

AUTONOMOUS MATERIALS SYSTEMS
BECKMAN INSTITUTE FOR ADVANCED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

UNIVERSITY OF ILLINOIS AT URBANA-CHAMPAIGN

Modeling of a New Composite Manufacturing Process Based on Frontal Polymerization

Prof. Philippe H. Geubelle
Dept. of Aerospace Engineering and Beckman Institute
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

In collaboration with
**Elyas Goli, Sagar Vyas, Nil Parikh,
Dr. Xiang Zhang, Prof. Nancy Sottos, Prof. Jeff Moore**

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Autonomic Materials Systems Team

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Composite Manufacturing Challenges

Boeing autoclave for curing large composite structures

Heated mold for wind turbine blade

Objectives

- To reduce **time to cure of thermoset composites** by (at least) **two orders of magnitude**
- To reduce **energy consumption** by (at least) **eight orders of magnitude**
- To **substantially reduce capital investment costs**

FP-Based Composite Manufacturing

Modeling: Homogenized Reaction-Diffusion PDEs

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\kappa} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + (1-\phi) \bar{\rho} H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \bar{\rho}^* \bar{C}_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) (1-\alpha)^n \alpha^m \left(\frac{1}{1 + \exp(c_d(\alpha - \alpha_d))}\right) \end{cases}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\kappa} = \kappa_m(1-\phi) + \kappa_f\phi \\ \bar{\rho} = \rho_m(1-\phi) + \rho_f\phi \\ \bar{C}_p = (C_p)_m(1-\phi) + (C_p)_f\phi \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A &= 8.55 \cdot 10^{15} \frac{1}{s}, & m &= 0.77, \\ E &= 110,750 \frac{J}{mol}, & n &= 1.72, \\ H_r &= 350 \frac{J}{g} \end{aligned}$$

DCPD	Carbon fibers
$\kappa_m = 0.152 \frac{W}{mK}$	$\kappa_f = 9.363 \frac{W}{mK}$
$\rho_m = 980 \frac{kg}{m^3}$	$\rho_f = 1800 \frac{kg}{m^3}$
$(C_p)_m = 1600 \frac{J}{kg.K}$	$(C_p)_f = 753.62 \frac{J}{kg.K}$

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FP in Carbon/DCPD Composite

$$\kappa \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + (1-\phi)\rho H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \rho^* C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$$

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) (1-\alpha)^n \alpha^m \left(\frac{1}{1 + \exp(c_d(\alpha - \alpha_d))}\right)$$

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Validation

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Non-Dimensional Form of PDE

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\kappa} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \bar{\rho} H_r (1 - \phi) \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \bar{\rho} \bar{C}_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) g(\alpha) \end{cases}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\kappa} = \kappa_m (1 - \phi) + \kappa_f \phi \\ \bar{\rho} = \rho_m (1 - \phi) + \rho_f \phi \\ \bar{C}_p = (C_p)_m (1 - \phi) + (C_p)_f \phi \end{cases}$$

Non-dimensional time $\tau = A t$

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\kappa} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \bar{\rho} H_r (1 - \phi) A \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \bar{\rho} \bar{C}_p A \frac{\partial T}{\partial \tau} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \exp\left(\frac{-E}{RT}\right) g(\alpha) \end{cases}$$

Non-Dimensional Form – Thermal Eqn.

Non-dimensional temperature $\theta = \frac{T - T_0}{T_{max} - T_0}$ where $T_{max} = T_0 + \frac{H_r(1 - \phi)}{C_p}$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\bar{\rho} A \bar{C}_p}{\bar{\kappa}} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\bar{\rho} A \bar{C}_p}{\bar{\kappa}} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau}$$

A dimensional analysis of the equation introduces an 'intrinsic length scale'

$$L = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\kappa}}{\bar{\rho} A \bar{C}_p}} \quad \text{Note: } L = f(\phi)$$

Non-dimensional spatial coordinate

$$\tilde{x} = \frac{x}{L}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial \tilde{x}^2} + \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau}$$

Note: no material parameters

Non-Dimensional Form – Cure Kinetics

Back to the cure kinetics equation

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right)g(\alpha)$$

Substitute

$$T = T_0 + \frac{H_r(1-\phi)}{\bar{C}_p} \theta$$

to get

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \exp\left(-\frac{\beta}{\theta + \gamma}\right)g(\alpha) \quad \text{with} \quad \beta = \frac{E \bar{C}_p}{R H_r (1-\phi)}$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\bar{C}_p T_0}{H_r (1-\phi)}$$

Non-Dimensional Form - Summary

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial \tilde{x}^2} + \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \exp\left(\frac{-\beta}{\theta + \gamma}\right)g(\alpha) \end{cases}$$

with

$$\beta = \frac{E \bar{C}_p}{R H_r (1-\phi)} \quad \gamma = \frac{\bar{C}_p T_0}{H_r (1-\phi)}$$

$$\tau = A t \quad \tilde{x} = \frac{x}{L} \quad L = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\kappa}}{\bar{\rho} A \bar{C}_p}}$$

$$\theta = \frac{T - T_0}{T_{max} - T_0} = \frac{\bar{C}_p}{H_r(1-\phi)}(T - T_0)$$

$$\beta, \gamma, \text{ and } L = f(\phi)$$

Non-Dimensional Form – Steady-State

Let $\tilde{y} = \tilde{x} - \tilde{V} \tau$ be (non-dimensional) coordinate attached to the front

where $\tilde{V} = \frac{V}{A L}$ is the (non-dimensional) front speed

Write $\tilde{\theta}(\tilde{y}) = \theta(\tilde{x}, \tau)$ and $\tilde{\alpha}(\tilde{y}) = \alpha(\tilde{x}, \tau)$

Applying the chain rule $\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau} = -\tilde{V} \frac{d\tilde{\theta}}{d\tilde{y}}$ and $\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tilde{x}} = \frac{d\tilde{\theta}}{d\tilde{y}}$

we get

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d^2 \tilde{\theta}}{d\tilde{y}^2} + \tilde{V} \frac{d\tilde{\theta}}{d\tilde{y}} - \tilde{V} \frac{d\tilde{\alpha}}{d\tilde{y}} = 0 \\ \frac{d\tilde{\alpha}}{d\tilde{y}} = \frac{-1}{\tilde{V}} \exp\left(\frac{-\beta}{\tilde{\theta} + \gamma}\right) g(\tilde{\alpha}) \end{cases}$$

Non-Dimensional Form – Steady-State

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d^2 \tilde{\theta}}{d\tilde{y}^2} + \tilde{V} \frac{d\tilde{\theta}}{d\tilde{y}} - \tilde{V} \frac{d\tilde{\alpha}}{d\tilde{y}} = 0 \\ \frac{d\tilde{\alpha}}{d\tilde{y}} = \frac{-1}{\tilde{V}} \exp\left(\frac{-\beta}{\tilde{\theta} + \gamma}\right) g(\tilde{\alpha}) \end{cases}$$

Boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\theta}(-\infty) &= 1 - \alpha_0 \\ \tilde{y} \rightarrow -\infty \quad \frac{d\tilde{\theta}}{d\tilde{y}}(-\infty) &= 0 \\ \tilde{\alpha}(-\infty) &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\theta}(\infty) &= 0 \\ \tilde{y} \rightarrow \infty \quad \frac{d\tilde{\theta}}{d\tilde{y}}(\infty) &= 0 \\ \tilde{\alpha}(\infty) &= \alpha_0 \end{aligned}$$

Non-Dimensional Front Speed vs. (β, γ)

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Dimensional Front Speed vs. (β, γ) - $\phi = 0$

Recall: $\tilde{V} = \frac{V}{AL}$

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Dimensional Front Speed vs. $(\beta, \gamma) - \phi = 0$

Front speed
(in mm/s)
for fixed $g(\alpha)$

$$\beta = 60.9$$

$$\gamma = 1.34$$

$$L = 3.37 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}$$

Key observation:
there is a front
speed for all (β, γ)

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Competition FP vs. Bulk Polymerization

To determine whether FP is possible to manufacture a part of size D , we need to compare the **time scale associated with FP**

$$t_{FP} = \frac{D}{V(\beta, \gamma)} \quad \text{or} \quad \tau_{FP} = \frac{D/L}{\tilde{V}(\beta, \gamma)} \quad \text{recall} \quad L = \sqrt{\frac{\kappa}{\rho A C_p}}$$

with the **time scale associated with bulk polymerization** computed from 0-D model (initial value problem)

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \exp\left(\frac{-\beta}{\theta + \gamma}\right) g(\alpha) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \tau} = \exp\left(\frac{-\beta}{\theta + \gamma}\right) g(\alpha) \end{cases} \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{cases} \theta(\tau = 0) = 0 \\ \alpha(\tau = 0) = 0 \end{cases}$$

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Carbon/DCPD: Front Speed vs. $(\beta, \gamma) - \phi = 0.2$

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Carbon/DCPD: Front Speed vs. $(\beta, \gamma) - \phi = 0.4$

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Conclusions Thank you

- Frontal polymerization is a promising, faster and energy-efficient way to manufacture high-quality composites
- Initiation and propagation of polymerization front in composite can be captured using a homogenized reaction-diffusion model
- Non-dimensional steady-state formulation reduces the model to two key non-dimensional parameters and allows for a rapid 'sweep' of different chemistries
- Next
 - Other chemistries (e.g., epoxy) and other reinforcements (e.g., glass)
 - Effect of n and m
 - Effect of boundary conditions
 - Design chemistry to maximize front speed and achieve high fiber volume fractions

$$\int \bar{\kappa} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \bar{\rho} H_r (1 - \phi) \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = \bar{\rho} C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$$

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